

Enhancing solar furnace performance by a robust QFT-based control approach

Abstract—This paper presents a control approach designed with Quantitative Feedback Theory (QFT) to regulate the temperature of material samples in a solar furnace situated at the Plataforma Solar of Almería¹. The parametric uncertainty of the linearized model is determined through experimental testing on the plant, involving multiple step changes in the shutter percentage and subsequent analysis of the system response. Afterwards, an uncertain linear representation of the system is employed to develop a QFT controller. The final control approach comprises a PI-based controller with a reference filter, a series feedforward to mitigate the effects of solar radiation disturbances, and a nonlinear element limiting the control signal, with an added anti-windup mechanism to ensure the system security. Finally, experimental tests demonstrate the satisfactory performance of the proposed control methodology across multiple operating conditions.

Index Terms—Robust Control, Frequency Design, Solar Energy, QFT

IN the face of accelerating climate change and its far-reaching consequences, transitioning towards renewable energy sources has never been more urgent. With rising temperatures, extreme weather events, and ecological disruptions becoming increasingly prevalent, the need to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and mitigate the impacts of global warming has become crucial.

Solar energy is a particularly compelling solution among many renewable energy options. Its outstanding efficiency and adaptability set it apart from other sources, making it a cornerstone of the renewable energy revolution [1]. Its versatility extends across several applications; it can undergo conversion into electricity through the use of photovoltaic panels [2], or it can be transformed into thermal energy via solar thermal collectors [3], showcasing its wide-ranging applications in sustainable energy generation.

Beyond its conventional role in power generation, solar energy shows versatility in practical applications such as high-temperature material synthesis and thermal stress testing [4]. Solar energy is a sustainable alternative to traditional heating methods in these domains, offering precise control over temperature and minimizing environmental impact. High-temperature material synthesis, for instance, relies on solar furnaces to generate the intense heat necessary for producing advanced materials like ceramics and semiconductors. By harnessing concentrated sunlight, these furnaces enable precise temperature regulation and facilitate the synthesis of materials with tailored properties. Similarly, solar energy finds utility in thermal stress testing, where materials undergo a

rigorous examination to assess their durability under extreme temperature conditions.

A solar furnace consists of a solar tracking collector system (heliostat) and a static parabolic collector that concentrates a significant amount of solar energy at its focal point, known as the test area for sample materials [5]. The intensity of incident light can be adjusted using a shutter located between the collector and the heliostat. Traditionally, solar furnaces have been operated manually. However, they can present difficulties due to the criteria required by the treatment processes, such as maintaining a precise temperature regulation. The temperature gradient of the piece must be respected in the tests, which is one of the main restrictions to avoid damaging it. Additionally, disturbances from direct radiation must be compensated for, such as passing clouds, which affect the temperature of the piece. That is why it is essential to have a control system that automatically meets all these requirements to avoid human error [6], [7].

Research efforts in applied control engineering for solar furnaces have been driven by the achievement of optimal results and efficiency [8]. Over the past years, significant progress has been made in this area. Various solutions have been proposed, ranging from the use of Proportional, Integral, and Derivative (PID) controllers to more advanced strategies. The work by [6] introduced PID-based control schemes that accounted for the non-linear nature of the system by using both fixed and variable parameters depending on the operating point. In [9] an enhanced disturbance accommodation controller strategy was developed. The authors in [10] presented a fuzzy controller for the copper sintering process within a solar furnace. In [8] a PI control strategy was suggested that incorporates a model-based feedforward (FF) control law with maximum positive and negative velocity phases to handle nonlinearities and system constraints. Moreover, the authors in [11] presented a similar approach involving a PI controller combined with a constrained feedback linearization strategy. In [12], the control strategy is based on the exact feedback linearization associated with PI and feedforward strategies. Furthermore, in [13] the authors proposed an exact linearization method combined with a PI controller, which also took active cooling into account. Other control techniques presented in the literature which are based on optimization have also been implemented in the real facility. The authors in [14] implemented a practical nonlinear model predictive control (PNMPC) in the solar furnace, and the results demonstrate its effectiveness in controlling the sample temperature during thermal stress trials. Moreover, authors in [15] presented two control strategies for temperature regulation in a solar furnace: the first used a two-degrees-of-

¹Based on experiments carried out at the Plataforma Solar de Almería

freedom scheme combining generalized predictive control with both nonlinear and linearized models to handle free and forced responses, while considering amplitude and slew-rate constraints; the second employed a constrained control approach that explicitly addresses both input and output constraints.

However, in the literature, there are not many robust controllers implemented in solar furnaces that capture plant uncertainty and designed for this purpose. In the work [16], an integrated approach was employed, combining a fractional PID controller with a gain scheduling scheme to effectively handle system nonlinearities and maintain satisfactory performance across various operating points. Therefore, further research and development in robust control for solar furnaces are needed, as they are highly nonlinear systems subject to disturbances and characterized by significant uncertainty.

Based on the above analysis, this article presents a robust PID control for regulating the temperature of a solar furnace. The main objective is to implement a single controller that manages to track the reference based on transient specifications, respecting the maximum temperature gradient constraint, and rejecting disturbances while considering the associated uncertainty and showing consistent dynamics for all operating points. To achieve this, it is necessary to determine the plant parametric uncertainty, accomplished through real open-loop experiments. Once the uncertainty is captured, a robust PI controller has been designed using quantitative feedback theory (QFT) [17] and successfully implemented on the real plant, yielding satisfactory results. Additionally, as calculated analytically, the closed-loop response remains within the limits imposed by the specifications across all operating points, exhibiting a very smooth and stable sample temperature evolution in all tests.

The paper's structure is organized as follows: In Section 2, the system is described, and the difficulties in modeling a solar furnace are outlined. Section 3 explains the foundation and design of the control architecture proposed. Section 4 illustrates the primary outcome achieved through the implementation of the suggested controller in the real facility. Lastly, Section 5 summarizes the key findings of the study.

I. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

This section provides an overview of the solar furnace used in this work. A nonlinear first-principles model describes the dynamic evolution of the piece temperature as a function of solar irradiance, shutter opening, and ambient temperature. This nonlinear model is linearized to obtain a first-order linear approximation for the dynamics of the system. Open-loop tests are then performed, covering all working temperatures to capture the parametric uncertainty of the approximate linear system.

A. Solar furnace description

The model of the SF60 solar furnace located at PSA used in this work is shown in Fig. 1. A scheme of the system is also represented in Fig. 2. It comprises a series of reflectors designed to concentrate solar radiation to perform thermal treatments on specific material samples placed at a focal point.

The primary concentrating element is a heliostat positioned outside the installation, which is responsible for concentrating solar radiation onto a shutter. It autonomously adjusts its position to track the Sun's trajectory. The heliostat at PSA consists of 117 flat facets, each with a surface area of 1 m^2 , and 52 flat facets with a surface area of 0.25 m^2 , totaling 130 m^2 [18].

Fig. 1: SF60 solar furnace located at the PSA (courtesy of the PSA, where the experiments shown in this paper have been carried out).

The shutter is the actuator used to control the amount of radiation reflected by the heliostat, which impacts the secondary concentrator within the installation. Solar radiation passes through the shutter and is directed onto a parabolic concentrator (a secondary concentrator), which further concentrates this radiation onto a focal point housing the test table. Thus, the shutter is positioned between the heliostat and the collector, and it comprises a series of metal slats with aperture

Fig. 2: Solar furnace diagram

ranges between 0% and 100%. In the actual PSA installation, a speed limitation is imposed on the actuators to prevent forceful actions. Under this condition, the shutter fully opens within 12 seconds, defining an opening speed of 8 %/s.

The parabolic concentrator consists of multiple mirrors that reflect incident radiation towards a specific focal point. Its total dimensions measure $11.40 \times 9.91 \text{ m}^2$, yielding a reflective surface area of $S_c = 108 \text{ m}^2$. The focal area, where 90% of the energy converges, corresponds to a circle with an area $S_{f90} = 0.038 \text{ m}^2$, situated at a distance of 7.8 m from the collector.

The sample material under test in this work is Silicon Carbide, with a dimension of $50.4 \times 50.3 \times 5.7 \text{ mm}^3$.

B. Model description

The dynamic progression of the sample temperature, contingent upon solar irradiance, shutter aperture, and ambient temperature, can be captured in a nonlinear first-principles model. This is obtained from the simplified energy balance described in [6], where its differential is given as follows:

$$m_s c_s \frac{dT(t)}{dt} = \frac{\rho_c \rho_h S_c}{S_{f90} \sin(\alpha_o)} S_s \alpha_a I(t) \left(\sin(\alpha_o) - \sin \left[\left(1 - \frac{u(t)}{100} \right) \alpha_o \right] \right) - \alpha_e \sigma S_s (T(t)^4 - T_a(t)^4) - \alpha_c S_s (T(t) - T_a(t)) \quad (1)$$

with the system output and input represented with the sample temperature $T(t)$ [K] and shutter opening $u(t)$ [%], respectively. The disturbance variables include the direct irradiance $I(t)$ [W/m²] and the ambient temperature $T_a(t)$ [K]. The description of model parameters and their respective values are shown in Table I.

Variable	Description	Value
c_s	Specific heat	1142 [J/(kg K)]
m_s	Sample mass	0.025 [kg]
S_c	Collector surface	108 [m ²]
S_{f90}	Focus surface	0.038 [m ²]
S_s	Sample surface	0.0025 [m ²]
α_a	Sample absorption capacity	0.5013 [-]
α_c	Convection losses coefficient	45.17 [W/(m ² K)]
α_e	Sample emissivity	0.5958 [-]
α_o	Maximum shutter angular opening	50.8 [°]
ρ_c	Collector reflectivity	0.9199 [-]
ρ_h	Heliostat reflectivity	0.9018 [-]
σ	Stephan-Boltzmann constant	$5.67 \cdot 10^{-8}$ [W/(m ² K)]

TABLE I: Parameters of the SF60 solar furnace model

To design a robust PID controller, it is necessary to estimate the parametric uncertainty bounds of a simplified model of the system. Hence, the linearization of the nonlinear model is carried out to study the linearized model parameters. Then, an open-loop test is done on the solar furnace plant to characterize the uncertainty of the parameters for the linearized system. Therefore, the nonlinear differential equation from (1) is linearized. The Taylor series was truncated in the first term, resulting in the linear model defined in Eq. (2). The deviation variables are defined as $\tilde{T}(t) = T(t) - \bar{T}$, $\tilde{I}(t) = I(t) - \bar{I}$,

$\tilde{T}_a(t) = T_a(t) - \bar{T}_a$ and $\tilde{u}(t) = u(t) - \bar{u}$, being \bar{T} , \bar{I} , \bar{T}_a and \bar{u} the values of each variable at the quasi-stationary operating point of the system, given slight fluctuations in irradiance over time.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\tilde{T}(t)}{dt} + (A_3 + 4A_2\bar{T}^3) \tilde{T}(t) = & \left(\sin(\alpha_o) - \sin \left[\left(1 - \frac{\bar{u}}{100} \right) \alpha_o \right] \right) A_1 \tilde{I}(t) + \\ & A_1 \frac{\alpha_o}{100} \bar{I} \cdot \cos \left[\left(1 - \frac{\bar{u}}{100} \right) \alpha_o \right] \tilde{u}(t) + \\ & (A_3 + 4A_2\bar{T}_a^3) \tilde{T}_a(t) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where the auxiliary constants A_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) are given by:

$$A_1 = \frac{\rho_c \rho_h S_c}{S_{f90} \sin(\alpha_o)} \frac{S_s \alpha_a}{m_s c_s}, \quad A_2 = \frac{\alpha_e \sigma S_s}{m_s c_s}, \quad A_3 = \frac{\alpha_c S_s}{m_s c_s}$$

Then, the Laplace transform is applied to express the model in the s domain, yielding the following expression:

$$\tilde{T}(s) = \frac{k_I}{(\tau s + 1)} \tilde{I}(s) + \frac{k_{T_a}}{(\tau s + 1)} \tilde{T}_a(s) + \frac{k_u}{(\tau s + 1)} \tilde{u}(s) \quad (3)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} k_I &= \frac{(\sin(\alpha_o) - \sin[(a - \frac{\bar{u}}{100})\alpha_o]) A_1}{A_3 + 4A_2\bar{T}^3} \\ k_{T_a} &= \frac{A_3 + 4A_2\bar{T}_a^3}{A_3 + 4A_2\bar{T}^3} \\ k_u &= \frac{A_1 \frac{\alpha_o}{100} \bar{I} \cdot \cos \left[\left(1 - \frac{\bar{u}}{100} \right) \alpha_o \right]}{A_3 + 4A_2\bar{T}^3} \\ \tau &= \frac{1}{A_3 + 4A_2\bar{T}^3}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

It can be observed how the system temperature variations around the actual operating point are defined from three first-order transfer functions. In this linearized model, $\tilde{u}(s)$ is the Laplace transform of $\tilde{u}(t)$, which represents the variations of the shutter aperture about the actual operating point. The same interpretation can be made in the case of the two main disturbances, given by ambient temperature variations (represented by $\tilde{T}_a(s)$ in Laplace domain) and direct irradiance variations (represented by $\tilde{I}(s)$).

On one hand, the ambient temperature term will not be considered as it slightly affects temperature control because it does not change substantially during operation. Nevertheless, it is essential to note that when identifying the uncertainty of the system, the influence that this term can have on the plant is included in it.

On the other hand, solar radiation is the most impactful measurable disturbance affecting the system, and to compensate for variations in solar irradiance, it is helpful to isolate the influence of this variable within the controller scheme. This disturbance will be compensated with a series FF controller. Its primary purpose is to assist the controller in mitigating disturbances arising from fluctuations in solar irradiance,

Fig. 3: Representative example of an open-loop test

notably due to cloud cover. Hence, the FF is defined as $FF = \bar{I}/I(t)$, making the open loop less susceptible to solar irradiance changes. Therefore, the first two transfer functions in Eq. (3) can be neglected in the subsequent analysis, and the gain of the third transfer function, given by k_u in Eq. (4), is computed using the average daily irradiance for \bar{I} parameter, (what increases parametric uncertainty).

In order to capture the possible uncertainty of the simplified model parameters, several open-loop tests were performed for different operating points. This way, a train of steps was chosen in the system working in a temperature range between 400 and 1100 °C, thus covering a wide working range where the system typically operates. The previously described feedforward control was incorporated into all the tests with $\bar{I} = 846.37 \text{ W/m}^2$. This value was selected based on the average radiation levels on sunny days during the month when the tests were conducted. In any case, any potential deviation will be compensated by the feedback controller. Fig. 3 illustrates an example for an open-loop test showing the temperature response to step changes in shutter opening, observed over a single test day. The two measurable disturbances, solar radiation and ambient temperature, are also represented.

Considering the linearized dynamics coupled in series with the FF compensator (see Fig. 4) and the process responses from the open-loop experiments, the following family of uncertain transfer functions is obtained by Eq. (5), where the static gain k_u and the time constant τ show considerable variation due to the nonlinear behavior of the system, that clearly behaves as a first-order system with dynamics depending on the shutter opening, the direct irradiance and the sample temperature at the focus point. Thus, the wide range of uncertainty justifies the use of a robust design technique to compute the controller.

$$\varphi = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} P(s) = \frac{k_u}{\tau s + 1}, \quad k_u \in [17.05, 49.34] \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}/\%, \\ \tau \in [22, 103] \text{ s} \end{array} \right\} \quad (5)$$

II. CONTROLLER DESIGN

This section presents the design of the proposed robust PID-QFT controller using the uncertain model introduced in the previous section.

The goal is to design a PID controller $C(s)$ [19], and a pre-filter $F(s)$, as depicted in Fig. 4 (where the back-calculation anti-windup mechanism [20] has been added to cope with saturation at the shutter), ensuring that all specifications are met for the plant family φ from Eq. (5) [21]. A proprietary MATLAB package has been utilized for controller computation [22], but any other tool for QFT design can be considered for this purpose.

Fig. 4: Closed-loop control scheme

The first step in QFT controller design is to define the stability and performance specifications that the closed-loop system must satisfy, defined in terms of inequalities on the closed-loop transfer functions, and the set of design frequencies. The specifications are frequency domain based, and for this system, a stability specification with a phase margin greater than or equal to 45° ($\lambda = 2.32 \text{ dB}$) for all operating points has been chosen [23], defined by Eq. (6).

$$\left| \frac{y}{rF} \right|_{dB} = \left| \frac{P(j\omega)C(j\omega)}{1 + P(j\omega)C(j\omega)} \right|_{dB} \leq \lambda, \forall \omega > 0, \forall P \in \varphi \quad (6)$$

For reference tracking, the specifications are given by Eq. (8) - (10), corresponding to a closed-loop time constant between 20 and 24 seconds, considering the following closed-loop transfer function:

$$|G_{ry}(j\omega)| = \left| \frac{F(j\omega)P(j\omega)C(j\omega)}{1 + P(j\omega)C(j\omega)} \right|_{dB} = \left| \frac{y}{r} \right|_{dB} \quad (7)$$

$$|B_l(\omega)|_{dB} \leq \left| \frac{y}{r} \right|_{dB} \leq |B_u(\omega)|_{dB}, \forall \omega > 0, \forall P \in \varphi \quad (8)$$

$$B_u(s) = \frac{\left(\frac{s}{0.1} + 1\right)}{\left(\frac{s}{0.0826} + 1\right)\left(\frac{s}{0.07} + 1\right)\left(\frac{s}{0.5} + 1\right)} \quad (9)$$

$$B_l(s) = \frac{\left(\frac{s}{0.1} + 1\right)}{\left(\frac{s}{0.03} + 1\right)\left(\frac{s}{0.035} + 1\right)\left(\frac{s}{0.2} + 1\right)\left(\frac{s}{10} + 1\right)} \quad (10)$$

Considering the model uncertainty shown in Eq. (5) and the previous specifications, a set of frequencies $W = \{0.01, 0.1, 1, 10\} \text{ rad/s}$ was selected, covering the system's operating range.

Fig. 5: Templates ($\omega_1 = 0.01$ rad/s, $\omega_2 = 0.1$ rad/s, $\omega_3 = 1$ rad/s, $\omega_4 = 10$ rad/s).

Once the set of design frequencies W has been defined, the uncertainty is represented in the Nichols plane for these frequencies, as shown in Fig. 5. A nominal plant $P_o(s) \in \wp$ defined in Eq. (11) is chosen within each template, marked with an asterisk.

$$P_o(s) = \frac{17}{22s + 1} \quad (11)$$

Next, based on the specified criteria and templates, for each frequency ω in the set W , restricted zones in the Nichols plane for the nominal open-loop transfer function are obtained [22]:

$$L_0(j\omega) = C(j\omega)P_o(j\omega)$$

These bounded zones are defined as boundaries, one for each frequency and defined specification. Fig. 6 shows the boundaries corresponding to the stability specification of 2.32 dB and the reference tracking specification, given by the difference in magnitude in dB of the bounds in Eq. (9) and (10), evaluated for frequencies in the set W .

With all boundaries defined, the open-loop function $L_0(j\omega)$ must have a shape that satisfies all limits for each frequency. Fig. 6 also depicts the adjustment of the nominal open-loop function for the tuned PID controller. The controller $C(s)$ and the filter $F(s)$ are given by the following equations:

$$C(s) = 0.1 \left(1 + \frac{1}{70s} \right) \quad (12)$$

$$F(s) = \frac{1}{18s + 1} \quad (13)$$

The final step in controller design is to validate if the specifications for frequencies outside the set W are met with the selected controller given by Eq. (6) and (8). Fig. 7 shows the validation of the design for tracking and stability specifications in the frequency domain.

Fig. 6: Adjustment of L_0 , fulfilling all stability and tracking boundaries ($\omega_1 = 0.01$ rad/s, $\omega_2 = 0.1$ rad/s, $\omega_3 = 1$ rad/s, $\omega_4 = 10$ rad/s).

Fig. 7: Frequency domain specifications validation

As defined in Section 2, three restrictions must be fulfilled on the control signal to implement the controller in the real facility. The first one corresponds to the amplitude saturation in the actuator. The input signal is limited to a maximum of $u_{lim} = 25\%$ aperture to prevent the piece from reaching too high temperatures. Additionally, the temperature gradient at the output is also limited to $\Delta T < 8^\circ\text{C/s}$, following the physical constraints of the sample at hand. This gradient corresponds to an approximation of the derivative of temperature over time in Eq. (1). Thus, the maximum control signal is defined by the following nonlinear equation:

$$u_{\Delta T} = 100 - \frac{100}{\alpha_o} \cdot \arcsin \left[\sin(\alpha_o) - \frac{S_{f90} \cdot \sin(\alpha_o)}{I \rho_c \rho_h \rho_c \rho_s \alpha_a} (\Delta T m_s c_s + B) \right], \quad (14)$$

where

$$B = \alpha_e \sigma S_s (T^4 - T_a^4) - \alpha_c S_s (T - T_a).$$

Fig. 8: Control scheme with anti-windup and control signal restrictions

Finally, according to the slew rate limitation of the actuator, the maximum speed of the control signal (shutter opening) is limited with $\Delta u/\Delta t < \Delta u_{max} = 8\%/s$. Then, assuming the sampling time as T_m , the following is obtained:

$$\Delta u = u(k) - u(k-1) < T_m \Delta u_{max}, \quad (15)$$

Therefore, the control signal applied in the real system is bounded by:

$$u_{max} = \min(u_{lim}, u_{\Delta T}, u(k-1) + T_m \Delta u_{max}) \quad (16)$$

As was previously commented, a back-calculation anti-windup mechanism [20] has been added to serve as security added when u is out of the interval $[0, u_{max}]$. In this case, the following tracking constant $T_t = 1/T_i$ is used. Fig. 8 represents the whole control scheme of the system.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, some illustrative results performed at the real facilities are shown and discussed. Fig. 9 and 10 show two different experimental tests for different days and operating point conditions. Furthermore, in these experiments, different setpoint profiles are introduced to analyze the response of the proposed control approach. All the variables affecting the system are displayed: The process output (sample temperature), the reference, the control signal (shutter opening), and the measurable disturbance (solar radiation). Notice that ambient temperature has not been included in the graphics due to its small value compared to the working temperatures.

Fig. 9 shows the first test performed in the real solar furnace with a step change response of 100°C amplitude within a range of 200 to 1000°C . The shutter value signal is the signal at the input of the shutter, and the shutter reference is the shutter opening computed by the proposed controller. Even with an adequate sampling time, these values can be different if communication problems happen between the PC running the control algorithm and the PLC driving the solar furnace. Despite the radiation disturbance, it is evident that the control system effectively tracks the reference changes, achieving good performance in the process output while complying with the applied control signal restrictions ($0 \leq u \leq u_{max}$),

denoted as shutter saturation in the graph). It is important to highlight the smoothness with which the temperature reaches the reference value.

Around 8:50 h, a communication failure is observed, returning to a steady state when it is back. It is also worth noting how, throughout the first half of the morning, radiation undergoes significant variations due to passing clouds. Despite this, the system effectively rejects them by following the reference, both in transient and steady-state conditions, thanks to the series feedforward. Moreover, this ability to adapt to the varying radiation conditions and in a wide operating range underscores the robustness of the system in maintaining desired performance levels despite external influences. Identifying instances where the control signal saturates (twice at 0%) is important for understanding the system limitations. Furthermore, the Eq. (16) provides a mathematical framework for defining the upper saturation limit, offering insight into system constraints. It can be observed in the figure how this limit changes during the day.

Fig. 10 shows the second test carried out on the real solar furnace. In this case, the step change has been set with 200°C of amplitude within a range of 200°C to 1000°C . Larger step changes were performed in this experiment. Throughout most of the test day, solar radiation remains relatively constant, albeit with fluctuations at the beginning of the day. Despite these disturbances, the system adeptly tracks the step changes, achieving an outstanding performance across all temperatures. Regarding the control signal, it is evident that it becomes more aggressive with higher changes in the reference step magnitudes. There is only one instance during the day where saturation occurs, towards the end of the experiment, which minimally impacts output performance thanks to the anti-windup mechanism added. Additionally, there is a communication fault similar to the previous test, occurring around 9.8 hours.

To evaluate the performance metric of the implemented controller, the closed-loop time constant was calculated for both tests across all reference changes. The mean and standard deviation values obtained are represented in Eq. (17).

$$\tau = 23.78 \text{ s} \pm 3.52 \text{ s} \quad (17)$$

Fig. 9: Test 1 in the real solar furnace with a 100°C amplitude step train in the temperature reference, sweeping from 300 to 1000°C.

Fig. 10: Test 2 in the real solar furnace with a 200°C amplitude step train in the temperature reference, sweeping from 200°C to 1000°C.

Fig. 11: Solar furnace limits for test 1 and test 2

Given that the design for reference tracking imposes a closed-loop time constant between 20 and 24 seconds (see Eq. (8)), it can be observed that the obtained values fall within the range specified, thereby meeting the imposed specifications for all operating points and different step input amplitudes.

Similarly, it can be seen that in all reference changes across both days of testing on the real facility, no overshoot occurs, except when the control signal saturates.

Finally, as presented in Fig. 11, the PI controller respects the actual operational and physical limits of the solar furnace, keeping the gradients within boundaries throughout the experiments.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents the implementation of a robust controller designed by QFT for temperature control in a solar furnace. Initially, the nonlinear system, a simplified linear dynamic model and the measurable disturbances are analyzed. Open-loop tests were then conducted on the nonlinear system to capture parametric uncertainty for the simplified linear model across all operating points. Afterwards, a PI controller was designed using QFT and combined with a series feedforward to compensate for the measurable disturbance of solar radiation. An anti-windup mechanism was also added to cope with the actuator saturation in amplitude and rate, and the gradient of the temperature in the solar furnace. The proposed control approach was evaluated with differing weather and operating conditions across two days. Despite fluctuations in disturbances and operating points, the control system successfully tracked the proposed setpoint changes. It is worth emphasizing how a single control scheme comprising the PID controller, a filter, the reference feedforward control, and a classical AW

scheme operates effectively for all operating points despite system nonlinearities and disturbances.

One key advantage of this work lies in its simplicity of implementation in the plant. It allows the operators to work with a straightforward control scheme that applies universally across desired operating points, eliminating the need to adjust parameters for any tests. On the other hand, given the contemporary importance of adopting renewable energy sources, the use of solar furnaces powered by clean energy sources is crucial in control applications. By harnessing the sun's renewable energy, this proposal control scheme for a solar furnace not only offers a sustainable solution for temperature regulation but also significantly contributes to mitigating carbon emissions and reducing environmental impact.

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